

Colour Contrast Analyser for Colour Blind Assessment

(Pembangunan Aplikasi Penilaian Kekurangan Penglihatan Warna)

Harhiviin a/l Ganesan, Kalaivani Chellapan

*Department of Electrical, Electronic and Systems Engineering,
Faculty of Engineering & Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Malaysia*
*Corresponding author: a163774@siswa.ukm.edu.my

ABSTRACT

Colour Vision Deficiency refers to the inability to distinguish different dominant colours. It is an inherited defect that causes damage or functionality weakness in one or more of colour receptors in the eye. There are many of well-known traditional clinical tests for colour vision deficiency diagnosis. One of these tests are by using the Ishihara Plates. In this project a Colour Vision Deficiency Testing Application is being developed to help users to determine the exact type of colour blindness they are experiencing. The methodology of this study was conducted through Matlab software. This Application can be used in colour vision education for school students and their teachers and parents also has the feature of colour vision screening. This paper focuses on the different type of plates that are combined as specific pattern's which will help users to discover their exact type of colour blindness. This application can identify if the user has Red-Green Colour Deficiency, Protanopia, Deutanopia or Monochromacy. A total of 39 users, 19 females and 20 males took part in using the application and a survey was conducted to collect the level of satisfaction of users regarding the application. The survey results show a high level of user experience satisfaction among users. The purpose of this project is to develop an application that is able to provide a high user experience among users in ensuring high accuracy in the deficiency detection.

ABSTRAK

Kekurangan Penglihatan Warna merujuk kepada ketidakupayaan untuk membezakan warna dominan yang berbeza. Perkara ini adalah kekurangan yang diwarisi yang menyebabkan kerosakan atau kelemahan fungsi pada satu atau lebih reseptor warna. Terdapat beberapa ujian klinikal tradisional yang terkenal untuk diagnosis Kekurangan Penglihatan Warna. Salah satu ujian terkenal adalah dengan menggunakan Plat Ishihara. Dalam projek ini, Aplikasi Penilaian Kekurangan Penglihatan Warna telah dikembangkan untuk membantu pengguna menentukan jenis buta warna yang mereka alami. Metodologi kajian ini dilakukan melalui perisian Matlab. Aplikasi ini boleh digunakan dalam pendidikan penglihatan warna untuk pelajar sekolah dan guru serta ibu bapa mereka juga mempunyai ciri penyaringan penglihatan warna. Projek ini memberi tumpuan kepada pelbagai jenis plat yang digabungkan sebagai corak tertentu yang akan membantu pengguna mengetahui jenis buta warna yang tepat. Aplikasi ini dapat mengenal pasti sama ada pengguna mempunyai Kekurangan Penglihatan Warna Merah-Hijau, Protanopia, Deutanopia atau Monokromasi. Sebanyak 39 pengguna, 19 perempuan dan 20 lelaki telah mengambil bahagian dalam menggunakan aplikasi ini serta sebuah tinjauan dilakukan untuk mengumpulkan data mengenai tahap kepuasan pengguna terhadap aplikasi tersebut. Hasil tinjauan menunjukkan tahap kepuasan pengalaman pengguna yang tinggi dalam kalangan pengguna. Tujuan projek ini adalah untuk mengembangkan aplikasi yang dapat memberikan pengalaman pengguna yang tinggi dalam kalangan pengguna bagi memastikan ketepatan tinggi dalam pengesanan Kekurangan Penglihatan Warna.

Keywords: Colour Contrast Analyser; Colour Blind Assessment; Ishihara Plates; Red-Green Colour Deficiency; Protanopia; Deutanopia; Monochromacy; Matlab; Application

INTRODUCTION

Colour vision deficiency refers to the inability of a person to distinguish between dominant colours. According to a biological interpretation, visual perception of colour is a process in which electromagnetic rays within a certain wavelength distance are absorbed by the retina of the eye thus converting it into an electrical signal, and then carried to the brain through the optic nerve (Gambino, O. et al. 2016).

Colour blindness is more common in males since X chromosomes carry the genes responsible for most common and inherited colour vision disorders and males have only one X chromosomes. In females, a functional gene on one of the two chromosomes is sufficient to compensate for loss on the other (Poret, S., Dony, R. D. & Gregori, S. 2009). About 8% of men and less than 1% of women have colour vision deficiency since birth (Ananto, B. S., Sari, R. F. & Harwahyu, R. 2011). Colour vision deficiency can be categorized light, moderate or serious. About 40% of students with lack of colour vision leave secondary school and are unaware that they are experiencing colour blindness (Harwahyu, R. et al. 2013).

There are various factors that cause a lack of colour vision. Most individuals who suffer from colour vision problems are due to genetics or inherited from their mothers. In addition, individuals can also become colour blind due to other diseases such as diabetes, multiple sclerosis or they get this disease over time due to the aging process. Most people who have colour vision problems can see clearly like other people however, they are not able to see red, green or blue light completely. It is very rare to find cases where an individual person is totally colour blind.

There are several types of colour vision deficiency. Among the types of colour vision deficiencies are Trichromacy, Red-Green deficiency, Dichromacy (Protanopia & Deutanopia) and Monochromacy. Most people experience Trichromacy vision which is also known as normal colour vision.

Red-Green colour blindness is one of the most common forms of hereditary Colour Vision Deficiency, characterized by complete loss or limited functionality of red cone and green cone photo pigment. It is a mild condition and does not hinder daily activities. Protanopia, a rare type of colour vision condition in which long wavelength receptors or known as L-cones did not form completely in the eye. In this, case, an individual person will have difficulty in identifying black, red, green, yellow and orange (Huang, J. et.al. 2009). Besides, an individual experiences Deutanopia when the medium wavelength receptors or known as M cones do not function. In this case, one cannot see

the green and magenta colours (Semary, N. A. & Marey, H. M. 2014). This colour vision deficiency is the most common. Monochromacy is the total inability to perceive colour. This type of colour blindness makes one see the world in shades of grey. Only a handful of humans who cannot see color directly (Ananto, B. S., Sari, R. F. & Harwahyu, R. 2011). It is very rare and is called monochromatic vision.

Many methods have been proposed to help individuals to determine whether they are experiencing colour blindness. The most basic and common test would be the Ishihara test. The test is named after Shinobu Ishihara, a professor at the University of Tokyo, who first published the test in 1917 (Ishihara, S. 1917). The test consists of several coloured plates referred to as Ishihara plates where each plate contains a circle of dots that appears randomly in colour and size (Kindel & Eric 2013). In this paper Ishihara test is used as the main source together with the developed application. The full Ishihara test consists of 38 plates.

FIGURE 1. All 38 Ishihara Test Plates

The first plate shown in the Ishihara test is called the Introduction Plate. The second plate till the 9th plate is known as the Transformation Plate. The 10th till the 17th plate are known as the Vanishing Plates. The 18th plate till the 21st plate is known as the Hidden Digit Plates. The 22nd till the 27th plate is known as the Classification Plates. Last but not least, 28th plate till the 38th plate contains lines (Laskowski, M. 2012). Plates that only carry lines are for individuals who are not good at reading numbers, they will track the lines contained in the plates from end to end using indicators. Moreover, these plates are most likely not used all the time. For this study, only plates containing numbers were used

to produce the colour vision assessment application. This is because plates that have lines are not suitable to use in the application because they cannot take advantage of the actual functionality. Each Ishihara test plate has a real function that many do not understand. From the studies that have been done, the Ishihara plates can determine the exact type of colour vision deficiency of a person precisely that many people do not realise. In the methodology of this study, it describes the actual function of Ishihara plates, the main reason Ishihara Plates were chosen and as well as how Ishihara Plates were divided into several main groups of pattern to benefit the main purpose of this study.

Among the problem statements of this study are individuals with colour vision problems will face problems in daily life, such as difficulty distinguishing the colour of clothing, signal lights, and certain symbols. People with poor colour vision often live many years without realizing that they have such deficiencies (Lee, J. & Dos Santos, W. P. 2010). In some cases, lack of colour vision can be an obstacle for individuals to pursue education or careers in certain fields if they are not detected since childhood (Harwahu, R. et al. 2013). This becomes even more serious if individuals do not know the exact type of colour vision problems they are experiencing. Thus, early tests of colour vision deficiency are essential to support individuals with this deficiency problem since the early phases of their lives (Gambino, O. et al. 2016).

The main objective of this study is to develop an application for colour vision deficiency assessment with the development of a computerised diagnosis system based on the existing manual evaluation process, traditional testing and online assessment tests. Based on the problems discussed, the main objectives of this study are as follows:

- a) Develop an application that is easy to use, exciting, and robust.
- b) Develop an application that can determine the exact type of colour vision deficiency.

METHODOLOGY

There are several steps followed to complete this study and to develop the proposed application. In the first stage, a visibility study on the Ishihara Test and Plates was conducted. The visibility study will be conducted by studying each plate contained in Ishihara test. Only several plates were chosen to conduct this study and to combine it together with the application. This step also includes planning on arranging the chosen plates in several groups of patterns. Then, the process of developing the application based on the ideation. After that, empathy method was used by conducting a survey on the satisfaction of users regarding the application

which will be discussed more at the end of this study. Lastly, improvements and modification will be done to fulfil people's expectations.

FIGURE 2. Flowchart of research method

Visibility Study of Ishihara Plates and Pattern Selection

In this study, 12 plates from the Ishihara test were selected and divided into three groups of patterns. This is done because each group has a specific reason which will be further explained. All Ishihara test plates are not required to determine the exact type of colour vision deficiency of a person. Therefore, this new technique was introduced in this study to further facilitate the process of determining the exact type of colour vision deficiency of a person.

As we know, the first plate (no. 12) shown in the Ishihara test is called the Introduction Plate. This plate is a compulsory plate to be chosen (Semary, N. A. & Marey, H.M. 2014). So in this study, this plate was made as the first pattern as shown in Figure 3. The main purpose of this plate is to test whether a user has prior colour vision. If a user

is unable to answer or detect the number on the first plate, the user is experiencing Monochromacy colour vision deficiency.

FIGURE 3. Pattern 1 of the Colour Contrast Analyser Application

As for the second group of pattern, only eight plates were selected from the 2nd plate till the 9th plate as shown in Figure 4, which is called the Transformation Plate of the Ishihara test and the 10th to the 17th plate which is called as the Disappearing Plates (Semary, N. A. & Marey, H.M. 2014). The purpose of this plates selection were because a user with normal colour vision will be able to accurately detect all these plates, but a person who suffers from red-green vision deficiency will have difficulty detecting it.

FIGURE 4. Pattern 2 of the Colour Contrast Analyser Application

As for the third group of patterns, three plates from the 22nd plate to the 27th plate of the Ishihara test called the Classification Plate are selected as shown in Figure 5. The purpose in selecting these plates because it helps to determine if

a person is suffering from a type of vision deficiency known as Protan (difficulty in seeing red colour). As for users who experience this situation, they can only see the number on the right side of the plate, whereas a person experiences Deutan will only be able to see the number on the left side of the plate (Semary, N. A. & Marey, H.M. 2014). The selection of these plates will provide an opportunity to further determine the two types of colour vision deficiencies known as Protanopia and Deutanopia.

FIGURE 5. Pattern 3 of the Colour Contrast Analyser Application

In overall, from this study we can conclude that all Ishihara plates do not need to be used to know the exact type of colour vision deficiency of a person. Some important plates are sufficient enough to determine the exact type of colour vision deficiency. For this study, only 12 plates were selected in total to be tested through the developed applications. The application being developed in this study using Ishihara plates as the main source will be able to determine each type of colour vision deficiency accurately of a person. Among the type of colour vision deficiency of a person that this application will determine are Monochromacy, Red-Green deficiency, Protanopia and Deutanopia. This is the main objective that distinguishes this study from other studies which uses almost the same concept.

Application Development and User Data Capturing

The application's interface was developed through App Designer Matlab software (Matlab 2021a). App Designer integrates the two primary tasks of app building, laying out the visual components of a graphical user interface (GUI) and programming app behaviour. App designer helps to develop the code and also allows to modify the code accordingly that satisfy the use of the application which is being

FIGURE 6. Flowchart on the operation of the Application's Interface accordingly

FIGURE 7. Colour Contrast Analyser Application Interface

This application allows users to test their colour vision which will be using the chosen plates from the Ishihara Test. To go through this test, users have to hit the “Open Image” icon present at the top left corner of the application’s interface as shown in Figure 6.

FIGURE 8. Snapshot of folder containing all 12 Plates

Following this, a folder containing all 12 will pop up as shown in Figure 7. This step enables users to start the test by choosing the 1st Plate to the 12th Plate accordingly one by one. The application expects users to fill in the number that he or she observe. The user is also required to answer all 12 Plates from the folder in order to know the exact type of colour vision deficiency he or she is experiencing. Furthermore, as the user answer each plate, the application automatically updates the users results into a table as shown in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9. Snapshot of users result automatically generated into a table

Users have to insert their details such as their Name, Age, and Gender. Furthermore, a screen will pop up indicating whether the user have answered the right answer. As the user answers each plate a pop up screen will indicate whether the person has a normal view or any type of colour vision deficiency

Wrong answer will indicate the user what type of colour vision deficiency he or she is experiencing accordingly to each plate they answer.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Design Results and Link Up with Data Recording

Upon completion, users can upload their result into the computer system by hitting the “Write to File” button present at the bottom left corner of the application’s interface as shown in Figure 10.

FIGURE 10. Snapshot of pop up screen indicating user has “Normal View” (Pattern 1)

FIGURE 11. Snapshot of pop up screen indicating user experiencing “Red Green Deficiency”

FIGURE 12. Snapshot of pop up screen indicating user experiencing “Deutanopia”

FIGURE 13. Snapshot of pop up screen indicating user experiencing “Protanopia”

FIGURE 14. Snapshot of app interface and pop up screen indicating results uploaded successfully into the system

This way helps the users to view their result after completion of the test using the application. From the table developed by the application, users can determine their exact type of colour vision deficiency.

Name	Age	Gender	Plate No.	Your Answer	Actual Answer	Red-Green Deficiency	Protanopia (CVD)	Deutanopia (CVD)
Mayghen	23	Male	1	12	12			
			2	29	29			
			3	15	15			
			4	74	74			
			5	97	97			
			6	45	45			
			7	7	7			
			8	16	16			
			9	73	73			
			10	42	42			
			11	35	35			
			12	96	96			
Afiqah	23	Female	1	12	12			
			2	70	29		70	
			3	17	15		17	
			4	21	74		21	
			5	nothing	97	nothing		
			6	nothing	45	nothing		
			7	nothing	7	nothing		
			8	nothing	16	nothing		
			9	nothing	73	nothing		
			10	42	42			
			11	35	35			
			12	96	96			

FIGURE 15. User response generated from the application (Normal View and Red-Green Deficiency)

From Figure 15 shows two example results of users. We can observe that from the generated table above, the application managed to determine whether the user has a “Normal View” of colours (Mayghen) or experiencing “Red-Green Deficiency” (Afiqah). From the results obtained by user Afiqah, it proves that Transformation Plates, from the 2nd plate till the 9th plate which were chosen to be the

second pattern in this study helps to determine the exact type of colour vision deficiency. Not only that, the application developed in this study successfully generated the table automatically which turns out to be an accurate result.

Name	Age	Gender	Plate No.	Your Answer	Actual Answer	Red-Green Deficiency	Protanopia (CVD)	Deutanopia (CVD)
Mohan	23	Male	1	12	12			
			2	29	29			
			3	15	15			
			4	74	74			
			5	97	97			
			6	45	45			
			7	7	7			
			8	16	16			
			9	73	73			
			10	4	42			4
			11	3	35			3
			12	9	96			9
Naim	23	Male	1	12	12			
			2	29	29			
			3	15	15			
			4	74	74			
			5	97	97			
			6	45	45			
			7	7	7			
			8	16	16			
			9	73	73			
			10	2	42			2
			11	5	35			5
			12	6	96			6

FIGURE 16. User response generated from the application (Deutanopia and Protanopia)

As we can see for the other two types of colour vision deficiency left, the application managed to generate an accurate result. We can observe that from the generated table above, the application managed to determine whether the user has experiences “Deutanopia” (Mohan) or experiences “Protanopia” (Naim). From the results obtained by user Mohan and Naim it proves that Classification Plates, from the 10th plate till the 12th plate which were chosen to be the third pattern in this study helps to determine the exact type of colour vision deficiency. Not only that, it is also proven that if a user managed to only see the number on the right of the plate he or she experiences Deutanopia (Mohan), whereas if a user managed to only see the number on the left of the plate he or she experiences Protanopia (Naim).

If a user is experiencing any type of colour vision deficiency, he or she can use this result to seek help and guidance from an expert eye doctor or else an ophthalmologist. In this case, the experts will definitely get a clearer picture of the deficiency problem the experts guidance will definitely help in reducing the problems faced due to colour vision deficiency faced by the individual in their daily live.

Statistical Analysis on Users Satisfaction Regarding Developed Application

A survey was carried out to do a statistical analysis on how the users preferred the application. This survey was filled by 39 users, 19 female and 20 male users who took the colour blind test through the developed application in this study. The 39 users were among age groups and race. The main purpose of this survey was to collect data on the satisfaction of users regarding the test carried through the developed application.

The survey was divided into three sections. Section A was on user satisfaction regarding the Application’s Interface. Section B was about user satisfaction on the Assessment Method done through the developed application. Section C was on the Result Satisfaction obtained by each user.

Each section consists of five questions respectively. Users level of satisfaction was collected in a way where users have to choose among Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree or Strongly Agree for each questions in the respective sections.

Section A (Assessment on the application’s interface) / (Penilaian Antaramuka Aplikasi)

FIGURE 17. Section A (User Satisfaction on Application’s Interface)

Section B (Assessment Method) / (Kaedah Penilaian)

FIGURE 18. Section B (User Satisfaction on Assessment Method)

Section C (Result Satisfaction) / (Kajian kepuasan hasil responden)

FIGURE 19. Section C (User Satisfaction on the Obtained Results)

Overall, from the statistical analysis done most of the users have chosen the option “Agree” and “Strongly Agree” for the questions asked in each section. Therefore, we can come to a conclusion that most of the users who took the test through the developed application in this study were really satisfied with the application’s interface, the assessment method through the application and the final result obtained. Not only that, the questions asked in the survey was really satisfied with the application’s interface, the assessment method through the application and the final result obtained. Not only that, the questions asked in the survey was also another way to find out whether the objectives of this study have been achieved. Both objective proposed in this study have been achieved successfully.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In a nutshell, all proposed objectives of this study have been successfully achieved. An application that is easy to use, exciting, and robust have been developed. Moreover, an application that can determine the exact type of colour vision deficiency of a person have also been developed.

Besides, there are certain limitations that this study can improve in the future. Among the limitations are this study only focuses on Ishihara Test as the main source. Other than that, this study is developed and also focuses on a single language. In this case, some users might find it hard to read and understand the terms and words used in the development of the application.

Therefore, the improvement that can be made to this study is that the application can be developed using more than one language. For example, the application can be developed with more than one language as English, Malay, Chinese and Tamil. This improvement will give an advantage to the users to choose their preferable language to answer the test using the developed application in this study. Moreover, another improvement that can be taken into consideration is to study and analyse more on other colour vision deficiency test and combine them together with the application in order to develop the perfect colour vision deficiency application that can determine the exact type of colour blindness of an individual.

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